

Research Role of Research Library

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Introduction: The ultimate goal of library is to provide information to the users within the reasonable time & cost team. Hence, we have to understand the information need of the users of the library. The primary factors that should govern collection building is the users need for information. If the libraries have to justify its existence & to serve their purpose, it is essential to study & access the needs for information of users systematically. In the library set up the user should be the central point around which all activities revolve. Users are the important factors without which an information system loses its whole purpose. To use is to put to some purpose thus the user of the system puts the system to its purpose. Particularly in library set – up it is extremely important to understand who the users are, what their needs are & how those needs can be satisfied by the library. To find out the answer of this question the user research is conducted.

Definition of use

‘To put something to its purpose’ Use:-To put something is its purpose User: - Someone who user

Client: -Person using the service of a professional

Patron: -Person giving influential or financial support to a cause Customer: - Buyer

Heidi Julien’s categorization of user as follows – “User: -This is the term that is generally employed to refer to client of information service & libraries, to particulars as respondent in research studies.

Client: -This term suggests a particular type of professional relationship

Customer: -This term is associated with a business model of service provision. It evokes notions of financial transactions.

Patron: - This term elicits image of wealthy benefactors & guardians”. Definition of user

A) According to type of work –

- 1) Lay people – basically the ‘ man on the street’
- 2) Government servants
- 3) Educators
- 4) Students
- 5) Researchers
- 6) Policy makers etc.

B) According to systems to which they belongs

- 1) Individuals house wives, farmers, social workers, ex- service man, laborers, student etc.
- 2) Government agencies & department: - administrators, policy makers etc.
- 3) Industrial enterprises : - managers, employees ect
- 4) Research Institutions or scientific organization: - researches, Scientifics etc.
- 5) Cultural organization Keepers of

cultural, musicians dances traditional Chit

- 6) Religious Organization – Pastors, priests, nuns, etc”

C) Other Categories of users

- 1) Professional – engineers, Medical practitioners, Managers, Scientists, lawyers etc.
- 2) Semi Professionals – Players, Cricketers, Midwives, Pharmacist etc.
- 3) Non professionals – laborers’, uneducated farmers, uneducated Housewives etc.

D) According to type of library :-

- 1) In a public Library – The users are mainly children, Student housewives, retired personsetc.
- 2) In a academic Library – the users are students, teachers & researches.
- 3) In special Libraries – The students are mainly researchers or specialists, who are specializing in a narrow field of subject.

Information use and user needs :-

To create information awareness & to promote the use of information explosion has resulted in an escalating growth rate of micro documents. Vis – a vis, the information needs of users has become varied & multidimensional. The information used needs both are directly concerned with users.

The users are the ultimate recipient of information in communication cycle. A user many belongs to user group with identifiable interest & environmental. The Individual as an user many be differ with regards to

- 1) Attitude, believe, values,
- 2) Goals
- 3) Capabilities
- 4) Communication attitude
- 5) Experience & habit
- 6) Cultural Background

The view points of users towards information varies according to the intended use. Although the uses in a particular working environment may have common view points & often shares the same priorities in the value of information. The dimension of use of information. Another dimension of the information use is the purpose for which it is being used that is research planning etc. The Information priority of user discipline. Depending on the role of a user time & not dependent on the user discipline. Depending on the role of a user the information priorities shift accordingly. For example.

A person may be researcher today, a planner, next, an information expert another day.

The collection and services of library should be tailored to meet the needs of users. This is possible only when we really understand their needs. Every one at various times needs information of one kind or another. The complexity in life is increasing simultaneously the volume of information, variety of media, & the means of access has also increased. On the other side the people tend to make only a minimum effort to obtain information. Hence the information agencies have to increase ease of use. The aim is to see that the users get the information they need.

Information needs of users:-

To understand the concept of 'information need' it is important to know the definition of the term 'need' In general need is Need - What a person ought to have Circumstances under which something is lacking therefore requiring some course of action That which one cannot do without That which is necessary for an organism's health & well being. The meaning of the term 'need' is related to the meaning of the terms requirement, want, demand the dictionary meaning of various related terms are "Need - want of something, which one cannot well do without.

Want: - a fact of being without or having an insufficient quantity, absence or deficiency of necessities.

Requirement: - A need, a thing needed a necessity Condon. Demand: - To require, asking for what is due asking for something" Definition of Information needs According to The librarian's Thesaurus - Information need is defined as " that need which library services or material are interred to satisfy.

Kinds of information needs:-

There are four kinds of information Needs.

- 1) Current information need
- 2) Exhaustive information need

- 3) Every day information need
- 4) Catching – up information need
- 1) Current information Need :-

In order to keep the users update with their respective fields of development. It is important to make available the right information in the right format of the seekers at the earliest possible. This need is more essentials in the fields of R & D institutions.

2) Exhaustive Information Need :-

This is required when a particular information user needs particular information exhaustively. Detailed information on a particular field helps the user to draw a suitable conclusion for the purpose.

3) Everyday information Need :-

As day to day activity vary from person to person different Kinds of users need different kinds of information at different points of time. There are some users who need information on a particular activity every day. This goes on changing from one day to another. Therefore everyday information is expected to be fast, reliable & up to date.

4) Catching up Information Need

This type of need is also known, as burnish – up needs. Brief & precise information are the characteristics of this kind of need of the users. The information should be as simple and to the point so that the users can easily catch it. This is an easy approach or access to information by the users in particular field activity. Which give the complete picture of that area in a precise form?

Kinds of user studies:-

There are different categories of user studies put forth by different people.

Line M.B. in his book 'Library survey, defines one type of user study 'The Survey'

'He defined the survey as "A systematic collection of data concerning a library, its activities, operations, staff, use & users at a given time"'.
Wilson - Davis put forth two categories of user studies –

1) Library oriented studies: - this study involves the investigation of how individual libraries or information centers are used.

2) User oriented studies: - This study explains how a particular user group obtains the information needed for the conduct of its work.

Menzel H categories –

A) User studies :-

Such studies try to find out the relative use of different channels in response to questions like, 'Where would you search for information?' or 'How did you find the reference ?' Such studies

have found that the common channels used by people include personal recommendations, abstraction & indexing services & (finding information) by change, regular perusal of journals etc. Example of such studies is "Scientists approach to information," by Melvin J. voight (1961)

B) Behavior studies

These are carried to find the pattern of the overall reaction of the user community to the communication system without referent to any specific ifromamtona receiving event. They basically study the communication behavior of the user one survey conducted by the "Operations research group of the case Institute of Technology" In 1958 found that scientists (chemists) generally spend almost half the time of their working hours in some form of communication such as consulting literature looking up for references, actually reading, talking or listening to a colleague & so on.

Information flow studies :-

These studies are conducted to find out the pattern of flow of information in the communication system. Example – an article is usually published in a journal 30 – 36 months after it has been written between the time it was written and the time it is published it flows through different stages of report preparation.

First the oral report at a conference. Then the technical report & finally. It is written for the journal.

Other Methods Feed – back service –

A library can acquire feedback information on the variety of services it provides. In the organization at SDI service, every document supplied to user is appended with feedback date card which contains questions as to the relevancy of information, timelines of supply & the descriptors use etc. the analysis of such data cards shows the efficiency of service & also provide considerable clue to build up pertinent user profiles.

Conclusion

Due to the information explosion it is impossible for people to grasp all the information that is being generated from various sources & presented in variety of forms. It is the duty of library and information centers to provide the needs of users & how these needs are satisfied. For this purpose libraries have conduct the studies of users to know their needs, requirement.

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